

Long-Term Changes in Strong Wind Duration and Intensity in Tel Aviv (1940–2025)

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Abstract

This study focuses on the impacts of climate change rather than theoretical meteorological modeling.

This work applies multi-threshold framework, the lowest strong wind threshold is 15 km/hr, the highest 40 km/hr, and each step 5 km/hr.

The highest annual mean wind speed in the period 1940-2025 was 11.9 km/hr, and the average 10.9 km/hr. The highest annual maximum wind speed in this period was 54.4 km/hr and the highest wind gust 99.7km/hr.

This work introduces the term “*Strong Wind Intensity Indicator*” (SWII) which is the product of the strong wind above the specific threshold by its duration.

The parameters analyzed are:

- average wind speed above thresholds
- annual duration of strong wind
- Strong Wind Intensity Indicator
- average continuous hours of strong winds
- maximum continuous hours of strong winds

Most parameters below 40 km/hr have decreased over the years, while lower wind speeds have resulted in a greater decrease.

The average velocity of change of winds above 40 km/hr in the last 31 years is 0.0531 km/hr per year.

The Strong Wind Intensity Indicator for wind speeds above 40 km/hr increased between 1940 and 2025 by an average of 2.53 km/hr per year.

Maximum continuous hours of strong wind speeds above 15 km/hr decreased by an average of 0.2 hour per year between 1940 and 2025.

Average and maximum wind gusts increased between 1940 and 2025 by 0.013 and 0.105 km/hr per year, respectively. However, wind gusts above 60 km/hr alone increased 0.022 and 0.238 km/hr per year, twice as much as all wind gusts.

Glossary

Ave	average
AveWS	annual average wind speed, km/hr
cHr	annual average continuous hours of Strong Wind per year, hr
cHr(15)	average continuous hours of Strong Wind per year, TSW=15km/hr
cHr(60)	average annual continuous hours of wind gusts above 60 km/hr
DSW	cumulative duration when wind speeds exceeded the TSW, hr/year
DSW(15)	cumulative duration when wind speeds exceeded 15km/hr TSW, hr/year
DWG(60)	cumulative duration when wind gusts exceeded 60 km/hr [hr/year]
MaxAveWS	maximum AveWS, km/hr
MaxcHr	annual maximum continuous hours when wind speeds exceeded the TSW, hr/year
MaxcHr(15)	annual maximum continuous hours of Strong Wind per year, TSW=15km/hr
MaxcHr(60)	annual maximum continuous hours of wind gusts above 60 km/hr
MaxWG	annual maximum wind gust, km/hr
MaxWS	annual maximum wind speed, km/hr
SW	annual average Strong Wind, in this work, mean wind speed above TSW, km/hr
SW(15)	annual average Strong Wind when wind speeds exceeded 15km/hr TSW, km/hr
SWII	Strong Wind Intensity Indicator - multiplication result of year average of SW speed by cumulative duration when wind speeds exceeded the TSW, km/year
SWII(15)	Strong Wind Intensity Indicator - multiplication result of year average of SW speed by cumulative duration when wind speeds exceeded 15km/hr TSW, km/year

TSW	Strong Wind Threshold, in this work, multi-threshold framework with stepping spectrum {15, 20, 25, 30, 35, and 40 km/hr}
WG	maximum wind gusts of the preceding hour 10m above ground, km/hr
WG(60)	wind gusts above 60 km/hr

Units

Wind speed and wind gusts at 10m above ground at the indicated hour (and not an average) of the last hour, km/hr.

The data are for Tel Aviv center @32.09139,34.782608.

Ground elevation 11.0m above the sea level.

Time is GMT+2 for the whole year, DST not considered.

Data Source

All data are from "Open Meteo - Historical Weather API" [1]-[5].

Wind speed and wind gusts are 10m above ground.

Wind speed is at the indicated hour, and not an average of the last hour, km/hr.

Wind gusts are maximum wind gusts of the preceding hour, km/hr.

Table 1 - Wind speed and wind gusts in Tel Aviv dataset [1]-[5]

	wind speed	wind gusts
data frequency	hourly	hourly
from date	01/01/40	01/01/40
to date	31/12/25	31/12/25
years	86	86
days	31,412	31,412
hours	753,888	753,888
records	753,888	753,888
missing	3	10
correct	753,885	753,878
units	km/hr	km/hr
resolution	0.1	0.1

The first 3 records in the wind speed and the first 10 records in the wind gusts datasets are missing.

The missing records on 1 Jan 1940 were determined based on the next day wind speed pattern at the relevant hours.

Table 2 - Estimation of missing wind speed records on 1 Jan 1940

	02/01/40	Δ	01/01/40
hr	km/hr	km/hr	km/hr
0:00	15.8		5.3
1:00	16.6	0.8	6.1
2:00	16.5	-0.1	6.0
3:00	17.4	0.9	6.9

Green – existing records, Red – estimated values

Table 3 - Estimation of missing wind gusts records on 1 Jan 1940

	02/01/40	Δ	01/01/40
hr	km/hr	km/hr	km/hr
0:00	29.5		41.3
1:00	32.0	2.5	43.8
2:00	29.2	-2.8	41.0
3:00	29.5	0.3	41.3
4:00	28.1	-1.4	39.9
5:00	28.1	0	39.9
6:00	29.9	1.8	41.7
7:00	29.5	-0.4	41.3
8:00	28.4	-1.1	40.2
9:00	27.7	-0.7	39.5
10:00	29.2	1.5	41.0

Green – existing records, Red – estimated values

Strong Wind Threshold - TSW

Table 4 - Annual average Wind Speed – AveWS, km/hr [1]-[5]

	AveWS, km/hr	year
Max	11.9	1953
Ave	10.9	1940-2025

The highest annual mean wind speed in the period 1940-2025, MaxAveWS, is 11.9 km/hr, and the average 10.9 km/hr.

Chart 1 - Annual average wind speed – AveWS, km/hr [1]-[5]

Chart 2 - Annual maximum wind speed – MaxWS, km/hr [1]-[5]

The highest annual maximum wind speed in the period 1940-2025 is 54.4 km/hr.

This work applies multi-threshold framework, the lowest Strong Wind Threshold is 15 km/hr, the highest 40 km/hr and each step 5 km/hr, resulting in stepping spectrum {15, 20, 25, 30, 35, and 40 km/hr} (TSW).

In this work the expression “*Strong Wind*” (SW) means the wind speed above the TSW.

Annual Average Strong Wind - SW

Annual average Strong Wind (SW) is regarded in this work as mean wind speed above the TSW threshold, km/hr.

Chart 3 - Trendlines of annual average Strong Wind - SW, for the whole spectrum of TSW threshold, km/hr

The chart above shows a slight decrease in SW(15) over the years and a slight increase in SW(35) and SW(40).

Chart 4 - Annual average Strong Wind, SW(40), TSW=40km/hr, km/hr

The average velocity of change of SW(40) in the period 1940-2025 is 0.0063 km/hr per year.

Chart 5 - Change in annual average Strong Wind, SW(40), TSW=40km/hr in years 1995-2025, km/hr

The average velocity of change of SW(40) in the last 31 years is 0.0531 km/hr per year.

Annual Strong Wind Duration - DSW

Chart 6 - Trendlines of annual Strong Wind duration - DSW, for the whole spectrum of TSW threshold, hr/year

The chart above shows a decrease in DSW(15) over the years and an increase in DSW(40).

Chart 7 - Annual Strong Wind duration, DSW(40) 1940-2025, hr/year

Chart 8 - Annual Strong Wind duration – SWII(40) 1995-2025 hr/year

Strong Wind Intensity Indicator - SWII

Strong Wind Intensity Indicator (SWII) is the multiplication results of year average of Strong Wind speed by cumulative duration when wind speeds exceeded the Strong Wind threshold.

Formula 1 - Strong Wind Intensity Indicator – SWII, km/year

$$SWII_k = \bar{U}_k \times D_k$$

$$k \in \{15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40\}$$

k	chosen Strong Wind threshold, km/hr
$SWII_k$	Strong Wind Intensity Indicator calculated at threshold k , km/year
\bar{U}_k	wind speed computed exclusively for hours exceeding threshold k , km/hr
D_k	cumulative duration when wind speeds exceeded threshold k , hr/year

As the wind speed is in km/hour units and cumulative duration in hours/year, the SWII results in km/year.

Formula 2 - Simplified formula of Strong Wind Intensity Indicator – SWII, km/year

$$SWII(TSW) = SW(TSW) * DSW(TSW)$$

TSW	Strong Wind Threshold, multi-threshold framework from 15 to 40 km/hr with 5km/hr stepping spectrum {15, 20, 25, 30, 35, and 40 km/hr}
SWII (TSW)	annual Strong Wind Intensity Indicator at selected threshold TSW, km/year
SW (TSW)	annual average wind speed in hours exceeding the TSW threshold, km/hr
DSW (TSW)	annual cumulative duration when wind speed exceeded the TSW threshold, hr/year

Chart 9 - Trendlines of annual Strong Wind Intensity Indicator – SWII, for the whole spectrum of TSW threshold, hr/year

The chart above shows a decrease in SWII(15) over the years and an increase in SWII(40).

Chart 10 - Annual Strong Wind Intensity Indicator – SWII(40) 1940-2025 km/year

Continuous Hours of Strong Wind - cHr

Chart 11 - Trendlines of annual average Continuous Hours of Strong Wind – cHr, for the whole spectrum of TSW threshold, hr

The chart above shows a decrease in continuous hours up to 40 km/hr and an increase above 40 km/hr.

Chart 12 - Average Continuous Hours of Strong Wind, cHr(40), hr/year

Maximum Continuous Hours of Strong Wind - MaxcHr

Chart 13 - Trendlines of annual Maximum Continuous Hours of Strong Wind – MaxcHr, for the whole spectrum of TSW threshold, hr

The chart above shows a maximum continuous hours decrease of up to 35 km/hr. The lower the wind speed, the greater the decrease.

Chart 14 - Maximum Continuous Hours of Strong Wind above 15 km/hr MaxcHr(15), hr

MaxcHr(15) decreased 0.2 hour per year between 1940 and 2025, on average.

Wind Gusts

Wind gusts are defined as the maximum wind gusts of the preceding hour.

Chart 15 - Annual average wind gusts above 60 km/y, WG(60), km/hr

Chart 16 - Annual wind gusts above 60 km/y duration, DGW(60), hours/year

Chart 17 - Annual average Continuous Hours of wind gusts above 60 km/hr – cHr(60), hours

Chart 18 - Annual maximum Continuous Hours of wind gusts above 60 km/hr – MaxcHr(60), hours

Chart 19 - Annual average wind gusts 1940-2025, km/hr

Average annual wind gusts increased by 0.013 km/hr per year between 1940 and 2025.

Chart 20 - Annual maximum wind gusts 1940-2025, km/hr

Maximum annual wind gusts between 1940 and 2025 increased by 0.105 km/hr per year.

Average Wind Speed, Maximum Wind Speed, Average Wind Gusts and Maximum Wind Gusts

Table 5 - Wind gusts (WG) and wind speed (WS) 1940-2025, km/hr

	WS	WG	WG-WS	WG/WS
Ave	10.9	21.3	10.4	1.95
Max	54.4	99.7	45.3	1.83

Chart 21 - MaxWS-AveWS, annual difference between maximum wind speed and average wind speed, km/hr

Chart 22 - MaxWS/AveWS, annual ratio of maximum wind speed to average wind speed

Chart 23 - MaxWG-AveWG, annual difference between maximum wind gusts and average wind gusts, km/hr

Chart 24 - MaxWS/AveWS, annual ratio of maximum wind gusts to average wind gusts

Chart 25 - AveWG-AveWS, annual gust-to-speed differential, km/hr

Table 6 - reason for the unusual peak in the gust-to-speed differential (AveWG - AveWS) in 2025, km/hr

AveWS	10.9
WS(2025)	8.8
WS(2025)-AveWS	-2.1
Ave WG	21.3
WG(2025)	23.3
WG(2025)-AveWG	+2.0
AveWG-AveWS	10.4
WG(2025)-WS(2025)	14.5
[WG(2025)-WS(2025)] - [AveWG-AveWS]	+4.1

In the above table:

AveWS mean annual average wind speed
 WS(2025) average wind speed in 2025
 AveWG mean annual average wind gusts
 WG(2025) average wind gust in 2025

The reason for the extreme peak in the gust-to-speed differential (AveWG - AveWS) in 2025 is not only the increase in wind gust, but also the decrease in average wind speed (AveWS) in 2025.

From 1940 through 2023, the annual average wind gust-to-speed differential (AveWG - AveWS) exhibited a highly stable baseline, fluctuating narrowly between 9 and 11 km/hr with a minor long-term linear increase of 0.02 km/hr per annum. However, the subsequent years marked a profound departure from this historical trend. In 2024, the parameter spiked sharply above the established trendline to 12.5 km/hr, an acceleration that intensified further in 2025, reaching an unprecedented peak of 14.5 km/hr.

Chart 26 - AveWG/AveWS, annual ratio of average wind gusts to average wind speed

Chart 27 - MaxWG-MaxWS, annual difference between maximum wind gusts and maximum wind speed, km/hr

Chart 28 - AveWG/AveWS, annual ratio of average wind gusts to average wind speed

Chart 29 - MaxWG-AveWS, annual difference between maximum wind gusts and average wind speed, km/hr

Chart 30 - MaxWG/AveWS, annual ratio of maximum wind gusts to average wind speed

Results Dataset

The dataset used in this work is publicly available in publication [6].

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